

Correlation between Emotional Intelligence and Organizational Commitment in IT Sector, Hyderabad

¹Dr. P. V. Varaprabhakar & ²Mr. T. Venkata Ramana

¹Research Supervisor & Assistant Professor, Department of Business Management, Yogi Vemana University, Kadapa, A.P. (India)

²Research Scholar, Department of Business Management, Yogi Vemana University, Kadapa, A.P. (India)

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*Corresponding Author

Email: venkatavaraprabhakar[at]gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The aim of this ponder was to research the relationship between sensational intelligence and organizational relegation in the IT sector, Hyderabad. Participants were all of software professionals (140) who were selected from IT sector, Hyderabad by convenient swatch and conform to two questionnaires: Cyberia-shrink sensational intelligence Questionnaire and Allen-Meyer organizational commitment. The event of retrogression analysis guides the indisputable significant relationship between emotive intelligence and organizational committees.

1. Introduction

Human force is the most essential strategic agent to increase the ability of the organism and therefore the evolution of the company. Scat and Zhaf (1999) consider the reduction and the capability of the man face as the vast advantage of a brigade incompetence with other organizations. In occurrence, the successful organizations are those which have competent and attached employees (Guenzi & Peelloni, 2004). Organizational reduction ignoble employee's positive or negative attitudes toward the regiment as a whole not their own definite stab in that organization.

An attached agent is trustworthy to his clique and ID himself via his membership of the system. The conception of organizational commitment is constructed of: affectional mittimus, Continuance weighty agent in the effectiveness of an association. On the other agent, human lard with moderate belief and relegation not only does not aid the organization to achieve its goals, but also defer its success (Jordan, 2002).

Many researchers in this room work to assume various factors influencing employees' commitment to the army and benefit their greatest capabilities. Emotional Intelligence (EQ) is one of the factors immanely authority the relationship between managers and members of the regiment. Goleman (1998) considers EQ as a main-hamper factor in a band. Emotional notice indicates methodical understanding, rate, and expressing emotions (Elks in & Elks in, 2003). Goleman (1995) expects that EQ contain: Self- Awareness, Self-Management, Motivation, Empathy, and Relationship Management (Abisamra, 2000). According to Mayer, Caruso and Salovey (2000) the most essential expertness of EQ is the impersonate's acquaintance of his emotions and feelings so that he can differentiate between his royal feelings and the unreal one. In the other words, EQ gives us the dexterity of enjoying our real feelings and to constitute the just decision in difficult circumstances. Barsad (2000) found out that increase of positive emotions in a group, and refute the members' ability. Gardner ad Stough (2003) measured that excitable intelligence is a utilitarian

prophet of job satisfaction and organizational warranty and is correlative with them. Results of Rozeman' study (2007) discloses that there is a significance instruction. Also, Norsidah (2008) found out that EQ can presage the organizational commitment; people with proud, emotional intellect have an mean even of organizational commitment. Rathi and Rastoghi (2009) in their contemplation concluded that there is an important indisputable relation between EQ and Job amends ad also an insignificant positive correlation between EQ and organizational consignment. Moreover, Organizational consignment and job satisfaction had a positive correlation. Othman and Anugerah (2009) showed that populate with high EQ are more attached to their jobs, warranty predicts stab satisfaction and committing Acts of the Apostles as a mediator between EQ and job recompense.

Reviewing the literature in this room disclose that in late organizations, managers, and employees can enhance assemblage esprit de corps and constitute the performance environment enjoyable by improving EQ factors. It seems that conspiracy of management knowledge and sensational capabilities can be advantageous to cause the people composition in management to win the organizational goals. Therefore, the coincident muse was to investigate the relationship between sensational intelligence, its aspects (self-awareness, unmixed-control, motivation, empathy, and relationship intrigue) and organizational commitment. Its' regard that the subclass of EQ can bode organizational commitment.

2. Method

2.1. Participants

The sample lien of all the IT professionals (140) that was culled from Hyderabad. They were all male employees, who were married, with undergraduate level of education with an age range of 25-45. Because of the restricted intention to congregate the participants, valid participants were culled as study samples.

2.2. Instrument

Organizational commitment spread: this scale has been constructed by Meyer and Allen (1990). It embody 24 questions in 5-Likert pen and 3 grinder-scales of affective Commitment, Continuance Commitment, and Normative Commitment. Reliability of the index was estimated 0.79 by Cronbach's alpha Coefficient.

Emotional Intelligence criterion: this questionnaire has been erect by Cyberia-Shrink (2010) and includes 33 doubt in 5-Likert manner and 5 sub-scales of self-awareness, self-management, motivation, empathy, and relationship management. Reliability of the register was estimated 0.63 by Cronbach's alpha Coefficient.

3. Results

To analyze the data, methods of descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation), Pearson correlation coefficient, and recession analysis were applied. Results are presented in table 1 to 3.

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Emotional Intelligence	140	3.76	.688
Self-awareness	140	3.74	.706
Self-management	140	3.84	.771
Motivation	140	4.27	.981
Empathy	140	3.60	.708
Relationship management	140	3.84	.771
Organizational commitment	140	3.84	.653
Affective commitment	140	3.79	.766
Continuance commitment	140	4.27	.812
Normative commitment	140	3.86	.607
Valid N (listwise)	140		

As the results of above table shows, motivation has the highest mean between sub-scales of emotional intelligence and continuance commitment has the highest mean between sub-scales of organizational commitment.

Variable	R	P
Emotional Intelligence	0.199	0.018
Self-awareness	0.61	0.472
Self-management	0.363	0.000
Motivation	-0.121	0.155
Empathy	0.111	0.153
Relationship Management	0.177	0.036

Results presented in table 2 shows that emotional intelligence and its sub-scales are significantly related to organizational commitment. Self-awareness has the highest correlation coefficient with organizational commitment.

Variable	β	t	p
Self-awareness	-0.032	-0.366	0.715
Self-management	0.303	3.362	0.001
Motivation	-0.079	-0.886	0.377
Empathy	0.115	1.357	0.177
Relationship Management	0.12	1.329	0.186

Results presented in a regression analysis show that Emotional intelligence and its sub-scales are significantly related to organizational commitment. Moreover Self-awareness ($R^2 = 0.53$, adjusted R square = 0.50), among the EQ's sub-scales, play the most important role in predicting organizational commitment.

4. Discussion

The findings of the meditation specify that there is an important rehearsal between the subjects' EQ and their organizational commitment. These effect are consistent with Othman and Anugrah (2009), Rozeman (2007), and Rathi and Rastoghi (2008). Rozeman (2007) in his muse found out that there is a significant relationship among variables of job content and organizational commitment and EQ. According to Salovey, Mayer, and Caruso (1998), the most intersecting aptitude of EQ is the person's awareness of his emotions and feelings so that he can desynonymize between his actual feelings and the imaginary once. In the other words, EQ gives us the skill to enjoy our kerçek feelings and to companion the right division in troublesome circumstances.

Results of retrogression analysis indicate a symbol positive relationship between subaltern-scales of EQ (selfishness-awareness, self-guidance, motivation, empathy, and relationship management) and organizational committal in the prone. Moreover, motivation, among the EQ's subaltern-scales, amusement the most important party in prediction organizational commitment. These findings are also resemblant to those of Carso (1998) and Gardner & Stough (2003). Caruso (1998) mention, name in Othman & Anugerah, 2009) found out that EQ and some of its substitute are correlated with organizational committal.

The result of these researches evince the momentous party of emotional news on organizational commitment, thus it present to managers to plan some instructive programs for employees to augment their spirit and emotional agent which can result in the virtue of the organizations.

This contemplation had some limitations, liking the limited multitude of sample adjust and nonrandom relish; those have limited the generalization of the results. Moreover, likely other meditation supported on self-echo questionnaire the partaker may have answered back untruly to the doubt.

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